

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING MEDIA COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: *Clarification of the theoretical and methodological aspects of the development of media competence indicators in future teachers based on the analysis of philosophical, pedagogical and psychological, technical and methodical literature and the strategic requirements of educational informatization is the basis of this article.*

Key words: *Media competence, information, methodology, indicator, didactics, strategy, pedagogy, scientific innovation, modeling, module, creativity.*

It is necessary to organize media competence as a study of a pedagogical phenomenon, that is, to determine its essence, properties, signs, content, to create a pedagogical model that allows the development of media competence in the process of professional training of future vocational education teachers in modern higher education institutions.

It is known that without studying the genesis of the phenomenon, its essence cannot be understood. Based on this, before developing the basic aspects of the problem of developing media competence in future professional education teachers and making proposals for its solution, we set out to study the history of the issue under investigation.

Comprehensive development of business, covering all sectors of the economy, has become the main trend of the beginning of the 21st century in our country. Every year, the need for competent future vocational education teachers who have all the

knowledge, qualifications and skills necessary for a modern manager is increasing. A large number of higher education institutions, including pedagogical higher education institutions, considered it necessary to train students in this field and included this direction in their curricula.

But due to the unabated need for teachers of future vocational education at all levels, high demands are placed on the knowledge and skills of future specialists. A modern competent future teacher of vocational education should have comprehensive knowledge, skills and abilities of his profession at the level of world standards, know pedagogical and information and communication technologies, be able to work actively with the media environment, z must be able to achieve the goals set before him, that is, in a word, he must be a media competent person.

In recent years, in the world, with the development of the theory of motivation and the evaluation of the professionalism of the teacher of the future vocational education and the stimulation of his activity; researches related to the development of potential are being carried out. However, nothing is blindly copied during this period, each source is carefully studied, and the content is creatively explored based on the actual conditions of meditation. The expansion of the global information space, including with the help of modern media, has created an opportunity for specialists to increase the level of media competence, independent education and independent development.

However, higher education institutions cannot train specialists without media education. This fact has created the conditions for the implementation of a large number of diverse studies carried out in recent years, in which the problems of developing media competence in future professionals, from future teachers to soldiers and engineers, have been studied. During this period, media competence of future vocational education teachers also became a subject of research due to the social order of the society for the knowledge and competence of specialists at all levels.

Summing up from the above, we can say that the issue of media competence development in future vocational education teachers is characterized by mass and

comprehensive study. Also, we emphasize that one of the priority tasks of our research is to search for and systematize the aspects related to the process of successful development of media competence, to raise this problem to the number of urgent issues of the development of general professional competence. During this period, against the background of existing social needs and economic conditions, the level and content of the educational subject "Educational Technology" will be consistently and comprehensively improved. This makes the problem of developing media competence one of the most urgent and important.

The problem we are studying is connected with the main changes taking place in the higher education system in our country, with the complete recognition of the competent approach as the basis of collective education, as well as with the fact that from year to year specialists of various fields, including the future profession we found out that it is characterized by the increasing number and quality of research on the development of media competence in education teachers.

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